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"LEONID: A CONSTELLATION OF LOVE"

Before you, love was just a word,
A whisper lost, a song unheard.
Then you appeared, a radiant gleam,
And painted life beyond my dream.

You are my harbor, safe and deep,
Where weary thoughts can fall asleep.
The laughter lines around your eyes,
Reflect a love that never lies.

Through tangled paths, we've walked as one,
Beneath the moon, beneath the sun.
You held my hand, you calmed my fear,
And whispered, "Darling, I am here."

The father's heart, so strong and kind,
In gentle lessons, peace we find.
You guide our children, hand in hand,
Across the sea, across the land.

And in the quiet of the night,
When stars emerge, with silver light,
I see your face, a timeless grace,
My Leonid, in time and space.

So let me hold you, close and near,
And banish every doubt and fear.
My husband, love, my guiding star,
Forever bound, no matter how far.